

CHEILOSIA CRASSISETA LOEW, 1859 (DIPTERA: SYRPHIDAE) FROM THE POLISH TATRA MOUNTAINS

CHEILOSIA CRASSISETA LOEW, 1859 (DIPTERA: SYRPHIDAE) Z POLSKICH TATR

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ABSTRACT. A review of the undetermined part of the material of the genus *Cheilosia* MEIGEN, 1838 in the Museum and Institute of Zoology, Polish Academy of Sciences in Warsaw, revealed a series of 4 specimens of *Cheilosia crassisetata* LOEW, 1859 from the highest parts of the Polish Tatra Mountains. This is the second known locality of this species in Poland.

KEY WORDS: Diptera, Syrphidae, *Cheilosia*, mountain species, Poland

INTRODUCTION

Cheilosia MEIGEN, 1838 is a genus of almost exclusively phytophagous Syrphidae flies, which are mostly black in appearance. Their larvae mine the stems, leaves, rosettes, bulbs or roots of various herbaceous plants as well as some conifers and fungi and in many cases they are highly host specific or even affiliated with specific parts of the plant (STUKE & CLAUSSEN 2000, GROSSKOPF 2005). Such a host plant association is known to have greatly promoted reproductive isolation and co-speciation, and together with the potential host switching processes influenced and led to high diversification of phytophagous insects (ARAÚJO *et al.* 2015). Indeed, almost one sixth of the number of the Syrphidae species occurring in Poland are *Cheilosia*. Some of the species are reported very rarely from the field, however once an appropriate biotope with their host plants is discovered and investigated in a timely manner, there is a chance one may find dozens of adult individuals of both sexes, crowding in a small territory.

A subgenus *Taeniochilosia* OLDENBERG, 1916 (= *Nigrocheilosia* SHATALKIN, 1975) consists of species with black legs and bare eyes and are well recognized taxonomically in Europe. It includes a large number of species, very similar to each other. In case of Poland, only three

of them are widespread and common: *Cheilosia pubera* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1838), *Cheilosia vicina* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1849) and *Cheilosia nigripes* (MEIGEN, 1822). All others should be treated as rare and seen as specialized mountain or submontane species.

Cheilosia crassiseta LOEW, 1859 was reported from Poland only once (BARKALOV & STÅHLS 1997) but without providing collection dates, based on a female specimen collected in Pieniny Mountains by K. WINNIK. Because in the MIZ PAS in Warsaw there are numerous specimens of other *Cheilosia*: *C. gagatea* LOEW, 1857 and *Cheilosia ruffipes* (PREYSSLER, 1793) [= *C. soror* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1843)] bearing the data on the label: "Pieniny, Trzy Korony, łąka ziołoroślowa [= Pieniny, Three Crowns, herbal meadow], leg. K. WINNIK" and only one date "27 VI 1973", it can be assumed that a specimen of *C. crassiseta* mentioned in that revision was caught on that day.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

During a review of undetermined Diptera material, mostly "diptera varia", in MIZ PAS (Museum and Institute of Zoology of the Polish Academy of Sciences), next to the main Syrphidae collection determined and organized by prof. R. BAŃKOWSKA-PISARSKA, a short undetermined series of *Cheilosia* from the high Tatra Mountains was found by the author in February 2019. As four of them appeared to be interesting small representants of the subgenus *Taeniochilosia*, a synthesis of information from descriptions and revisions (LOEW 1859; BECKER 1889, 1894; BARKALOV & STÅHLS 1997; CLAUSSEN & VAN DE WEYER 2004) was used in the aim of detailed identification of those individuals. Genital capsules of males were extracted and glued onto the additional label, then placed under the pinned specimens, to enable making photographs and additionally support identification.

RESULTS

Cheilosia crassiseta LOEW, 1859 (FIG. 1.)

MATERIAL. Tatra Mountains, Czerwone Wierchy, 1920-2120 m a.s.l., 26 VI 1956, 2♂♂ 2♀♀, leg. B. PISARSKI, coll. MIZ PAS.

DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES (IMAGINES). A series of four tiny (6 – 6.5 mm) specimens bearing the same handwritten label, fitted the original detailed description by LOEW (1859) of *C. crassiseta*. They differ from all other *Taeniochilosia* specimens present in revisions of BECKER (1889, 1894), BARKALOV & STÅHLS (1997) and CLAUSSEN & VAN DE WEYER (2004). Two male specimens collected by B. PISARSKI are almost identical to each other, only difference being that one of them has the 3rd segment of the antennae completely black, whereas the second has a slightly reddish posterior corner. Among other diagnostic features they have black, slightly hairy arista tightened from the middle of its length, 3rd segment of antennae a bit rectangular but with rounded corners, two-sized (long black and short white) pubescence on thorax and pubescent posterior anepisternum. They have the dorsal part of the thorax without any visible pubescence markings. Two female specimens, however, show some differences from each other in the thorax pilosity (presence versus

absence of a few longer black bristles among short light hairs), the hue of the 3rd segment of antennae (falling into red in posterior half versus completely black), pubescence of sternites II-IV (equally pubescent comparing to 1st segment as opposed to more shiny than that), black hairs on scutellum (present versus absent), shape of the facial knob (small and elongated versus more broader and massive), but are identical in all other characters and body size, including characteristic depressed and parted outwards hairs on the tergites III and IV as described by LOEW (1859) and visualized by CLAUSSEN & VAN DE WEYER (2004). Interpretation used here is they are both in the scope of intraspecific variability of one species. Variations in some diagnostic features of *C. crassiseta* are reported in literature since the original description, e.g., “♂, the rounded third segment [of antenna] sometimes reddish-brown” (LOEW 1859); “♂ and ♀, sometimes has red-brown antennae, a variety that is designated as such in Loew's collection.” (BECKER 1889); “♂ and ♀, third antennal segment small, rectangular with rounded corners, brownish to blackish, sometimes with lower posterior corner reddish” (BARKALOV & STÄHLS 1997); “♀, scutellum margin with a few short black bristles or without” (BARKALOV & STÄHLS 1997). A side effect of that variability is that females of *C. crassiseta* were placed three times in the determination key of BARKALOV & STÄHLS (1997) that was modeled after the key of BECKER (1894).

DISTRIBUTION. Known localities of *Cheilosia crassiseta* are in the high mountains of Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Italy, Montenegro, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia and Switzerland (LOEW 1859; VUJIĆ 1996; BARKALOV & STÄHLS 1997; DUNK 1999; SOMMAGGIO 2010; VAN STEENIS *et al.* 2013; VAN STEENIS *et al.* 2015).

FIG. 1. *Cheilosia crassiseta* LOEW, 1859 from Tatra Mountains: 2 ♂♂ 2 ♀♀.

NOTES ON THE BIOLOGY. Not much is known about the biology of *Cheilosia crassiseta*, except the fact that the imago is reported almost exclusively from high mountains in Europe and it lives on the alpine grasslands and hilltops (VAN STEENIS *et al.* 2015). The host plant is still unknown, however based on analysis of a limited set of potential hosts in the plant communities endemic to the Tatra Mountains occurring on moist gravel and granite screes of the mountain (1800-2400 m a.s.l.), and the fact that larvae of related *C. pubera* were described as narrowly monophagous from *Geum rivale* L. (STUKE & CARTENSTER 2002), one can set a hypothesis that larvae of *C. crassiseta* develop in lower parts of creeping avens *Geum reptans* L., the distribution of which is only high altitudes and extends from the Alps to the Carpathians, the Illyric mountains and Macedonia (PLUESS & STOCKLIN 2004), perfectly matching the known distribution of *C. crassiseta*, or in alpine avens *Geum montanum* L., which has a similar and slightly broader distribution.

NOTES ON THE LOCATION IN POLAND. Czerwone Wierchy in Tatra Mountains is a massif consisting of four hills in a row: Ciemniak – 2096 m, Krzesanica – 2122 m, Małołączniak – 2096 m and Kopa Kondracka – 2005 m, divided by three passes: Mułowa – 2067 m, Litworowa – 2037 m, Małołączka – 1924 m, located at a border between Poland and Slovakia. The name “Czerwony Wierchy” (*eng.* Red Peaks) comes from the red-brown color of their slopes, which is given to them by a plant *Juncus trifidus* L., which turns red in autumn, or sometimes in the middle of summer (FIG. 2).

FIG. 2. Locality of *Cheilosia crassiseta* LOEW, 1859 in Poland. Red Peaks (*pol.* Czerwone Wierchy) in Tatra Mountains. PHOTO: RAFAŁ CELADYN.

SUMMARY

The Diptera of the higher parts of the Polish part of the Tatra Mountains are poorly recognized and probably there are still species new to the Polish fauna and new to science to be found here (KLASA & PALACZYK 2010). Considering the endemic character of the plant communities of the subalpine and alpine layers it would be especially interesting to recognize the endemic phytophagous fauna associated to those herbs. In case of Syrphidae, there was practically no research done in the highest parts of Polish Tatra since field trips of NOWICKI (1867, 1868), LOEW (1870), BOBEK (1890) and MALSKI (1959). The unavailability of some of areas, unpredictable weather, as well as a short flight periods of imagines of Syrphidae, make any systematic field research on Syrphidae in the area difficult. Nowadays it is also an area highly protected by the Tatra National Park and proper permits for research are required. In this context every piece of information on the biology of these animals is valuable.

Specimens published in this work and found in MIZ PAS collection are rather accidental findings of prof. BOHDAN PISARSKI (1928-1992), collected at the beginning of the series of his expeditions on Hymenoptera. His visit in Tatra Mountains around the date of finding of *C. crassiseta* can be confirmed with a date of another Syrphidae specimen (*Sphaerophoria*) present in the material sections of BAŃKOWSKA (1964). B. PISARSKI was an entomologist specializing in myrmecology (CZECHOWSKI 1994), employed for 43 years in Institute of Zoology of Polish Academy of Science and in the years 1982-1992 was director of the institute (TROJAN & KAZUBSKI 1993; TROJAN 1994). He was also the second husband of PROF. REGINA BAŃKOWSKA-PISARSKA (1930-2017), a known Polish syrphidologist.

Taeniochilosia is overall difficult subgenus in *Cheilosia* and most of the older literature information about it still requires verification, by careful examination of the historical material deposited in museums. Two species in the subgenus *Taeniochilosia* require further revision the most (in the sense of their real distribution in Poland, if any): *Cheilosia antiqua* (MEIGEN, 1822) and *Cheilosia sahlbergi* BECKER, 1894, because those names were used historically for specimens of a few species being recognized nowadays.

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STRESZCZENIE

Cheilosia crassiseta LOEW, 1859 (Diptera: Syrphidae) z polskich Tatr

Podrodzaj *Taeniochilosia* OLDENBERG, 1916 (= *Nigrocheilosia* SHATALKIN, 1975) fitofagicznego rodzaju *Cheilosia* MEIGEN, 1838 obejmuje muchówki bzygowate o czarnych odnóżach i nieowłosionych oczach i jest dość dobrze rozpoznany taksonomicznie na terenie Europy.

W trakcie przeglądu nieoznaczonych okazów z rodzaju *Cheilosia* MEIGEN, 1838 w Muzeum i Instytucie Zoologii Polskiej Akademii Nauk w Warszawie odnaleziono krótką serię okazów z najwyższych partii polskich Tatr (Czerwone Wierchy) zebranych w ciągu jednodniowej wyprawy przez B. PISARSKIEGO w 1956 roku. Cztery osobniki (2 ♂♂ 2 ♀♀) to przedstawiciele górskiego gatunku *Cheilosia crassiseta* LOEW, notowanego wcześniej z Polski tylko raz - z Pienin (BARKALOV & STÄHLS 1997).

Muchówki wyższych partii Tatr są w Polsce wyjątkowo słabo rozpoznane. Biorąc pod uwagę endemiczny charakter zbiorowisk roślinnych piętra alpejskiego należy spodziewać się tam obecności kolejnych bardzo rzadkich lub nienotowanych jeszcze z Polski fitofagicznych gatunków muchówek.